

Evaluation of the Scientific Studies on Hemoptysis and Their Relationship with the COVID-19 Pandemic

Hemoptizi Konusundaki Bilimsel Çalışmaların Değerlendirilmesi ve Bunların COVID-19 Pandemisiyle İlişkisi

 Hüseyin Evren EREN

Department of Thoracic Surgery, Amasya University Sabuncuoğlu Şerefeddin Training and Research Hospital, Amasya, Türkiye

ABSTRACT

Aim: Hemoptysis is defined as the expectoration through the mouth of blood originating from the parenchymal tissue of the lung or from the bronchial tree. It is commonly seen throughout the world. The etiology of hemoptysis, which is widely encountered worldwide, has varied according to geographical conditions and the period in which the studies were conducted; in the face of this situation, it is observed that different countries have from time to time contributed to the scientific world through collaboration. The purpose of the study is to examine and evaluate the studies on hemoptysis from various perspectives.

Material and Method: A bibliometric and science mapping analysis was conducted using records retrieved from PubMed After applying eligibility criteria, 892 records published between 1845 and 2025 were included. Data were analyzed using the bibliometrix package in R.

Results: Hemoptysis-related publications increased over time. The most productive source was Chest, followed by Cureus and The Annals of Thoracic Surgery. The leading productive countries included China, India, Italy, Japan, and the United States, while the strongest international collaboration was observed between China and the United States.

Conclusion: Thematic analyses showed that the literature mainly focused on diagnosis, etiology, imaging methods, treatment outcomes, and clinical management.

Keywords: Hemoptysis, bibliometric analysis, science mapping

ÖZ

Amaç: Hemoptizi, akciğer parankim dokusundan veya bronş ağacından kaynaklanan kanın ağız yoluyla tükürülmesi olarak tanımlanır. Dünya genelinde yaygın olarak görülür. Dünya çapında sıkça rastlanan hemoptizinin etiyojisi, coğrafi koşullara ve çalışmaların yürütüldüğü döneme göre değişiklik göstermiştir; bu durum karşısında, farklı ülkelerin zaman zaman işbirliği yoluyla bilim dünyasına katkıda buldukları gözlemlenmektedir. Bu çalışmanın amacı, hemoptiziyle ilgili çalışmaları çeşitli açılardan incelemek ve değerlendirmektir.

Gereç ve Yöntem: PubMed'den elde edilen kayıtlar kullanılarak bibliyometrik ve bilim haritalama analizi yapılmıştır. Uygunluk kriterleri uygulandıktan sonra, 1845 ile 2025 yılları arasında yayınlanmış 892 kayıt çalışmaya dahil edilmiştir. Veriler, R yazılımındaki bibliometrix paketi kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir.

Bulgular: Hemoptiziyle ilgili yayınlar zaman içinde artış göstermiştir. En verimli kaynak Chest dergisi olmuş, bunu Cureus ve The Annals of Thoracic Surgery dergileri izlemiştir. En verimli ülkeler arasında Çin, Hindistan, İtalya, Japonya ve Amerika Birleşik Devletleri yer alırken, en güçlü uluslararası işbirliği Çin ile Amerika Birleşik Devletleri arasında gözlemlenmiştir.

Sonuç: Tematik analizler, literatürün ağırlıklı olarak tanı, etiyojisi, görüntüleme yöntemleri, tedavi sonuçları ve klinik yönetime odaklandığını göstermiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Hemoptizi, bibliyometrik analiz, bilim haritalama

Corresponding Author: Hüseyin Evren EREN

Address: Department of Thoracic Surgery, Amasya University Sabuncuoğlu Şerefeddin Training and Research Hospital, Amasya, Türkiye

E-mail: erenhuseyin785@gmail.com

Received/Başvuru Tarihi: 18.06.2026

Accepted/Kabul Tarihi: 25.06.2026

INTRODUCTION

The number of publications on hemoptysis increased over time, with a visible rise in the period temporally corresponding to the COVID-19 pandemic. However, this observation refers only to publication activity and should not be interpreted as evidence of an increase in the clinical incidence of hemoptysis. .

Although the etiology of hemoptysis varies according to geographical conditions, socioeconomic level, and the time interval in which the studies were carried out, in developed countries the most frequent causes of hemoptysis are acute bronchopneumonia due to nonspecific infectious causes, bronchiectasis, and pulmonary neoplasms. In developing countries, on the other hand, specific endemic diseases such as tuberculosis come to the fore. In conclusion, malignancy, pneumonia, lung abscess, bronchiectasis, and tuberculosis are the most common causes of hemoptysis.

The purpose of the study is to examine and evaluate the studies on hemoptysis from various perspectives. In line with this main aim, answers to the following questions were sought:

- What is the distribution of studies on hemoptysis by year?
- Which journals have published the most studies on hemoptysis?
- To which countries do the most studies on hemoptysis belong?
- Which countries produce the most studies on hemoptysis through collaboration?
- Which countries have published the most studies on hemoptysis by year?
- What are the niche, motor, basic, and emerging themes in studies on hemoptysis?

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study used the science mapping method to examine the bibliometric structure and thematic development of PubMed-indexed publications on hemoptysis. Science mapping enables the visualization of the development, structure, dynamics, and prominent elements of a scientific field. (1). Since this study also aimed to examine and evaluate the field of hemoptysis in terms of various variables, the science mapping method was adopted.

Documents

Within the scope of the research, since it is the most widely used search platform in the health literature, studies on hemoptysis published in journals indexed in the PubMed database were examined, and the studies obtained were acquired through the PubMed platform (2).

A PubMed search was conducted using the search strategy “(“Hemoptysis”[Mesh] OR hemoptysis[Title/Abstract])”. The initial search yielded 1,416 records. To ensure that the bibliometric analysis focused on scholarly and scientifically interpretable records, publication types that did not represent substantive scientific contributions were excluded. These included editorials, comments, letters, news items, interviews, biographies, dictionaries, directories, patient education handouts, retractions, expressions of concern, and video/audio materials. After applying the document-type eligibility criteria, 892 records were included in the final bibliometric analysis. The study-selection process was summarized in a PRISMA-style bibliometric workflow diagram to improve transparency.

Graph 1. PRISMA-style bibliometric workflow of the study-selection process

The diagram shows the number of records identified, the number of records excluded according to publication type, and the final number of records included in the bibliometric analysis. Information regarding the documents analyzed in the study is shown in **Table 1**.

Variable	Result
Time span (years)	1845–2025
Number of documents	892
Number of sources (journals, books, etc.)	1658
Number of authors	33502
References	45000+
Number of keywords	16851

As seen in **Table 1**, data regarding a total of 892 studies between the years 1845 and 2025 were analyzed according to the relevant criteria. These studies contain information on a total of 33502 authors and 1658 sources. More than 45000 reference entries and 16851 keywords are also included in the data set.

Analysis of the Data

All information regarding the 892 studies and the sources in which the studies were published was downloaded as a text file by selecting the “All Results” option and the PubMed format as the format. The data belonging to the 892 studies were analyzed using the bibliometric analysis method. In this method, the metadata of the studies obtained on the subject under investigation are analyzed quantitatively (3).

The data obtained were analyzed with the bibliometrix package of the R program. The bibliometrix package of the R program, with which data obtained from the PubMed database can be used and analyzed, is able to create comprehensive and explanatory visuals. With R bibliometrix, which is open source and free, analyses such as co-authorship, co-word, citation, co-citation, and bibliographic coupling can be performed (4). Due to these possibilities it offers, the bibliometrix package of the R program was used in this study for the analysis of the studies on hemoptysis.

RESULTS

In the study, the finding regarding the distribution of studies on hemoptysis by year was first obtained. The distribution of studies on hemoptysis by year is shown in **Graph 2**.

Graph 2. Annual scientific production

When **Graph 2** is examined, the number of hemoptysis-related publications indexed in PubMed appears to increase over time. A visible increase in publication output was observed in the years surrounding 2019–2020, which temporally coincides with the COVID-19 pandemic period. However, because the present study is based on bibliometric publication data rather than clinical incidence data, this finding should be interpreted only as an increase in publication activity, not as evidence of an increase in hemoptysis occurrence.

One of the findings obtained in the study also concerns the sources in which the studies addressing hemoptysis were published. The sources with the most studies addressing hemoptysis are shown in **Graph 3**.

Graph 3. Most relevant sources

When **Graph 3** is examined, it is seen that the source/journal with the most studies addressing hemoptysis is the journal “Chest,” with 451 studies. After “Chest,” the journals with the most studies addressing hemoptysis were determined to be, respectively: “Cureus” with 326 studies, “The Annals of Thoracic Surgery” with 179 studies, “BMJ Case Reports” with 135 studies, “Respiratory Medicine Case Reports” with 133 studies, “Medicine” with 124 studies, “Kyobu Geka: The Japanese Journal of Thoracic Surgery” with 99 studies, “Archivos de Bronconeumología” with 91 studies, “Nihon Kokyuki Gakkai Zasshi = The Journal of the Japanese Respiratory Society” with 85 studies, and again “Radiology Case Reports” with 85 studies.

In the study, findings were also obtained regarding the studies carried out through collaboration by researchers in different countries. Collaboration between countries is shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Country collaboration map

As shown in **Figure 1**, the strongest international collaboration in hemoptysis-related publications was observed between China and the United States. Other notable country collaborations included the United States–India, China–Germany, France–United Kingdom, United States–Pakistan, United States–United Kingdom, Italy–United Kingdom, United States–Canada, United States–Germany, and United States–Nepal collaborations. These findings indicate that international collaboration in the hemoptysis literature is concentrated mainly among countries with high publication productivity and established biomedical research networks.

Countries of the collaborating researchers	TNP
CHINA – USA	15
USA – INDIA	8
CHINA – GERMANY	7
FRANCE – UNITED KINGDOM	6
USA – PAKISTAN	6
USA – UNITED KINGDOM	6
ITALY – UNITED KINGDOM	5
USA – CANADA	5
USA – GERMANY	5
USA – NEPAL	5

TNP: Total Number of Publications

When **Table 2** is examined, among the studies addressing hemoptysis, the China–USA and USA–India collaborations stand out the most. In addition, it is striking that studies carried out through collaboration were mostly conducted with researchers in countries whose native language is English. Furthermore, it is observed that collaboration is concentrated in Western and Northern Europe.

In the study, findings were also obtained regarding the publication production rates over the years of the top five countries that publish the most on hemoptysis. These findings are shown in **Graph 4**.

Graph 4. Country production over time

In **Graph 4**, it is seen that the researchers who publish the most on hemoptysis are in China, India, Italy, Japan, and the USA. Although the USA, which is the place where publications on hemoptysis are produced most, has led the way over the years, it is striking that in recent years researchers in China have produced more publications on the subject and, in recent years, have produced more publications than those produced in the USA.

Among the findings obtained in the study, the trending topics related to hemoptysis over the last 15 years are also included. The findings regarding the trending topics are shown in **Graph 5**.

When **Graph 5** is examined, among the topics that have been trending in the last 15 years are: consensus, hemoptysis/etiology/diagnosis, carcinoma/non-small-cell lung/pathology, mutation, lung, computed tomography angiography, bronchi/diagnostic imaging, cough, thoracic surgery/video-assisted/methods, young adult, bronchoscopy/methods, retrospective studies,

treatment outcome, hemoptysis, tomography/x-ray computed, biopsy, and prognosis. It is seen that the studies between 1995 and 2005 were mostly studies focused on basic diagnosis and prognosis. After 2005, on the other hand, diagnostic methods and clinical evaluations were determined to be trending.

Graph 5. Trend topics

In the study, findings were obtained regarding the niche, motor, basic, and emerging themes related to hemoptysis. These findings are shown in **Graph 6**.

Graph 6.

When **Graph 6** is examined, the thematic map suggests that hemoptysis research is organized around several thematic clusters. Themes located in the upper-right quadrant may be interpreted as relatively central and developed themes, whereas those close to the axes should be interpreted with caution because small changes in centrality or density values may alter their quadrant classification. Therefore, clusters such as elderly patients and follow-up studies were described as relatively central and developed rather than definitively classified as motor themes. Similarly, embolization and angiography were located in the lower-left quadrant, which is generally interpreted as representing either emerging or declining themes. However, because the present analysis does not provide sufficient temporal evidence to distinguish emergence from decline, these themes were described more cautiously as low-centrality and low-density themes requiring further longitudinal evaluation. In the study, findings were also obtained regarding the grouping of the key terms used in the hemoptysis literature according to their similarities to one another. These findings are shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2.

When **Figure 2** is examined, it shows that the hemoptysis literature is shaped around several main thematic axes, namely patient demographics, diagnostic methods, clinical outcomes, and treatment approaches. While demographic variables and follow-up-related concepts cluster together, diagnostic and imaging methods form a separate sub-cluster. In addition, concepts related to etiology and differential diagnosis stand out as an independent group. These findings show that hemoptysis research is predominantly concentrated on diagnostic evaluation and clinical management.

DISCUSSION

Hemoptysis is the expectoration through the mouth of blood originating from the pulmonary or bronchial system. In most patients, the amount of hemoptysis is minimal and stops spontaneously. However, in rates ranging between 5% and 14%, massive hemoptysis is encountered, which is severe enough to endanger the person's life and to require urgent intervention (5,6). In a study conducted by Balcı et al., bronchoscopic treatment was applied to 11 (5.5%) of the patients, surgical treatment to 6 (3%), and embolization treatment at an external center to 1 (0.5%) patient. Symptomatic treatment was applied to 89 (44.5%) of the patients, while 93 patients (46.5%) were only followed up (7).

Hemoptysis is most frequently caused by lung cancers, tuberculosis, pneumonia, and bronchiectasis (8). In countries with low socioeconomic levels, infectious diseases, especially tuberculosis, are in the foremost place; whereas in developed countries, malignancies are more prominent (9). It is commonly seen worldwide in both developed and developing countries. The etiology of hemoptysis varies according to geographical conditions, socioeconomic level, and the time interval in which the studies were conducted.

In the studies conducted between 1845 and 2025, it is seen that the average number of publications increased after the second half of the 20th century. The greatest increase, on the other hand, occurred between the years 2019 and 2020. With the COVID-19 pandemic that began in 2019, an increasing number of hemoptysis cases are being reported in the medical coronavirus literature (10). The increase in hemoptysis-related publications during the period corresponding to the COVID-19 pandemic may reflect increased scientific attention to respiratory symptoms, pulmonary complications, and COVID-19-related case reporting. Nevertheless, the present study does not include patient-level clinical data or disease-incidence data. Therefore, no conclusion can be drawn regarding whether COVID-19 increased the occurrence of hemoptysis. The findings should be interpreted strictly as publication trends within the PubMed-indexed literature.

It was seen that the source with the most studies addressing hemoptysis is the journal "Chest," and that the studies are frequently published in journals specific to the subject. However, it may be considered that, as a result of changes in the etiology of the subject and the developments accelerating in diagnosis and treatment in recent years, publications in different groups of journals will also increase.

When the studies on hemoptysis are examined, it was determined that the researchers with whom researchers from different countries collaborated most are the researchers of the USA and the People's Republic of China. With the COVID-19 pandemic, it was determined that the country in which the subject is predominantly discussed and the number of studies has increased is the People's Republic of China.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the analysis was based only on records indexed in PubMed; therefore, studies indexed in other databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, Embase, or Google Scholar may not have been captured. Second, language and indexing bias may have influenced the findings, particularly for publications from regional or non-English journals not indexed in PubMed. Third, thematic map interpretations should be considered exploratory because centrality and density values were not reported for all clusters, and themes positioned close to the axes may be sensitive to classification changes. Finally, PubMed provides limited citation metadata compared with citation-focused databases, and the 2025 data should be interpreted with caution because it represented an incomplete publication year at the time of data retrieval.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, hemoptysis-related publications indexed in PubMed increased over time, and publication activity was higher in the period corresponding to the COVID-19 pandemic. However, this study analyzed publication metadata only and did not evaluate clinical incidence, patient-level outcomes, or pathophysiological mechanisms. Therefore, the observed increase should be interpreted as a bibliometric publication trend rather than evidence that COVID-19 increased the occurrence of hemoptysis.. Particularly together with developing technology, it may be assessed that studies on different techniques related to diagnostic methods will increase and, accordingly, that there will also be changes in current clinical approaches.

ETHICAL DECLARATIONS

Ethics Committee Approval: Ethics committee approval is not required for this study.

Informed Consent: Informed consent is not required for this study.

Referee Evaluation Process: Externally peer-reviewed.

Conflict of Interest Statement: The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Financial Disclosure: The authors declared that this study has received no financial support.

Author Contributions: All of the authors declare that they have all participated in the design, execution, and analysis of the paper, and that they have approved the final version.

REFERENCES

1. Cobo MJ, López-Herrera AG, Herrera-Viedma E, Herrera F. SciMAT: A new science mapping analysis software tool. *J Am Soc Inform Sci Technol.* 2012;63(8):1609-30.
2. Misra DP, Ravindran V. An overview of the functionalities of PubMed. *J R Coll Physicians Edinb.* 2022;52(1):8-9.
3. Büyükkıdık S. A Bibliometric Analysis: A Tutorial for the Bibliometrix Package in R Using IRT Literature. *JMEEP.* 2022;13(3):164-93.
4. Derviş H. Bibliometric Analysis using Bibliometrix an R Package. 2019;8(3):156-60.
5. Hirshberg B, Biran I, Glazer M, Kramer MR. Hemoptysis: etiology, evaluation, and outcome in a tertiary referral hospital. *Chest.* 1997;112:440-4.
6. Lordan JL, Gascoigne A, Corris PA. The pulmonary physician in critical care. Illustrative case 7: Assessment and management of massive haemoptysis. *Thorax.* 2003;58:814-9.
7. Balcı A, Çilekar Ş, İbrahim Coşğun İG. Hemoptysis etiologies and treatment approaches in patients presenting to our clinic with the complaint of hemoptysis. *Kocatepe Med J.* 2021;22:197-201.
8. Çolak M, Aslaner MA. Etiological Evaluation in Patients Presenting with the Complaint of Hemoptysis. *Sakarya Med J.* 2019;9(4):626-31.
9. Sakr L, Dutau H. Massive hemoptysis: an update on the role of bronchoscopy in diagnosis and management. *Respiration* 2010;80(1):38-58.

10. Yılmam İ, Karlıkaya C, Serez Kaya B, Kula O, Emmungil H. A life-threatening haemoptysis case that would have been defined as idiopathic before the COVID-19 era. *Tuberk Toraks* 2021;69(4):561-6.